

Approximate Structured Singular Value Computation via Frobenius Norms

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ABSTRACT

Two algorithms are presented to aid in the approximation of the structured singular value through minimization of the Frobenius norm. The first algorithm allows the uncertain terms to be complex. The second algorithm considers only real variations for real uncertain terms. An example problem is included and advantages and disadvantages are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The structured singular value analysis technique was developed in an attempt to quantify multi-input, multi-output (MIMO) system robustness. A measure was sought to determine whether a system would remain stable when subjected to uncertainty. Doyle [1] defined the structured singular value as such a measure for complex scalar and norm bounded uncertainties (μ_c). Because this measure was very difficult to calculate, Doyle defined an approximation to it in terms of an upper and lower bound. Jones [2] used Doyle's upper bound with Osborne's technique [3] to obtain an approximation for μ_c based on minimization of the Frobenius norm.

The calculations for μ_c assume that all uncertainties are complex. For problems involving parameter uncertainties that can only vary in a real manner, this consideration of complex uncertainties leads to overly conservative results. To address this problem, Jones [2] extended Doyle's method to approximate the structured singular value allowing consideration of only real variations for real parameters (μ_r).

The first algorithm presented is designed to approximate the upper bound for μ_c based on the work of Doyle ([1]) and Jones ([2]). The second algorithm is based on [2], and is designed to approximate μ_r as defined by Jones. Both algorithms use Osborne's technique as the optimization tool and are based on the block diagram formulation presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1

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This paper is arranged as follows: The next section includes the mathematical definitions necessary for understanding the structured singular value technique and the algorithms presented here. The following two sections include a brief discussion of the development of μ_c and the algorithm to compute it. The development of μ_r and the corresponding algorithm are presented in the next two sections. An example problem is included to show the results of the algorithms in relation to the exact result. Advantages and disadvantages of the algorithms and methods are discussed followed by the conclusion and list of references.

MATHEMATICAL DEFINITIONS

The following definitions are based on [1], [2], and [4]:

M-the transfer function matrix from uncertain inputs (outputs of Δ) to uncertain outputs (see Figure 1). **M** is a function of frequency, however, for ease of notation, it is written as **M** instead of **M**(s).

Δ -a block diagonal uncertainty (or perturbation) matrix which may contain scalar and/or norm bounded matrix variations.

$\|A\|_2$ -Two-norm of matrix **A**.

$$\|A\|_2 = \max_i \sqrt{\lambda_i(A^*A)}$$

$\|A\|_F$ -Frobenius norm of the matrix **A**.

$$\|A\|_F = \sqrt{\text{sum}(\text{diag}(A^T A))}$$

$\bar{\sigma}(A)$ -maximum singular value of matrix **A**. $\bar{\sigma}(A) = \|A\|_2$

k_{bar} -a vector with 2q elements given as

$$k_{bar} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_q, m_1, m_2, \dots, m_q]$$

where k_i is the number of times Δ_i is repeated in Δ , m_i is the dimension of Δ_i ($m_i \times m_i$), and q is the number of unique uncertainties.

D-set of block diagonal matrices of the form $D = \text{diag}(d_1 I_{m_1}, d_2 I_{m_1}, \dots, d_{k_1} I_{m_1}, \dots, d_{k_q} I_{m_q})$, where k , m , and q are defined above, and d_i is a positive real number.

X_∞ -set of all block diagonal matrices with structure defined by k_{bar} with no restriction on norm.

X_δ -set of all block diagonal matrices with structure defined by k_{bar} with norm bounded by δ .

I_q^n -set of all $2^q n \times n$ matrices of the form

$$\text{diag} \left((-1)^{j_1} I(k_1), (-1)^{j_2} I(k_2), \dots, (-1)^{j_q} I(k_q) \right)$$

where j_i is an arbitrary integer, $n = \sum_{i=1}^q k_i$, and q and k_i are defined above.

DEVELOPMENT OF μ_c

Figure 1 shows a closed loop representation of a real uncertain system. M contains the nominal plant, controller, and information about the anticipated uncertainty. Δ is a block diagonal matrix that accounts for norm bounded system uncertainties. The controller contained in M has been designed to stabilize the nominal system. The goal is to determine whether or not the controller also stabilizes the uncertain system.

It is known that the open loop system (given by the transfer function $M\Delta$) is stable. The "smallest" Δ of the form dictated by k_{bar} that will make $\det(I + M\Delta) = 0$ represents the maximum uncertainty the system can handle without becoming unstable. The size of Δ is determined through the use of the 2-norm. The inverse of the size of the smallest Δ that will drive the system unstable is given the symbol μ_c (subscript c denotes complex variations). Doyle has posed this problem as

$$\mu_c(M) = 0 \text{ if no } \Delta \in X_\infty \text{ solves } \det(I + M\Delta) = 0 \quad (1)$$

otherwise

$$\mu_c(M) = \min_{\Delta \in X_\infty} (\bar{\sigma}(\Delta) : \det(I + M\Delta) = 0)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

and shown that the stability criterion is $\mu < 1/\delta$ where δ is equal to the maximum subblock norm of Δ . Equation (1) indicates that there is no Δ of the correct form that will drive the system unstable. Equation (2) states that the robustness measure, μ_c , is equal to the inverse of the size of the smallest Δ that will drive the system unstable. If $\mu_c < 1/\delta$, then the system will be robust to the anticipated uncertainty.

The system given in Figure 1 can be rearranged so that each subblock of Δ has the same norm. Equation (2) can then be rewritten as

$$\mu_c(M) = \left\{ \min_{\Delta \in X_\delta} (\bar{\sigma}(\Delta) : \det(I + M\Delta) = 0) \right\}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

For this paper, δ is chosen to be unity.

Equation (3) represents an optimization problem that is difficult to solve due to the presence of local minima. To address this problem, Doyle [1] derived an expression for an upper bound for μ_c :

$$\mu_c(M) \leq \min_{D \in \mathcal{D}} (\bar{\sigma}(DM D^{-1})) \quad (4)$$

The right hand side of (4) represents an optimization problem with no non-global minima. This optimization involves finding the best D to minimize the maximum singular value (2-norm) of $DM D^{-1}$. Jones [2] has shown that Osborne's technique can be used to find the best D to minimize the Frobenius norm of $DM D^{-1}$. Because the Frobenius norm serves as an upper bound to the 2-norm, reducing the Frobenius norm reduces the 2-norm [2]. The best D found from Osborne's technique can be used in the right hand side of (4) to obtain an approximation to the upper bound for μ_c .

ALGORITHM TO APPROXIMATE μ_c

This algorithm is designed to aid in approximating μ_c based on Equation (4) given the transfer function matrix M for a problem involving q unique, non-repeated, independent uncertainties where each subblock of Δ is norm bounded by 1.

μ_c is a function of frequency, so it is necessary to evaluate $\bar{\sigma}(DM D^{-1})$ over a relevant frequency range.

In the algorithm below, Osborne's technique is used to find the best D (in terms of minimizing the Frobenius norm) to minimize $\bar{\sigma}(DM D^{-1})$. Due to space limitations, the details of the technique are omitted. See [2], [3], or [5] for additional information.

Algorithm 1

1. For the frequency sweep,
 - a. choose an initial frequency, ω_i ,
 - b. choose a final frequency, ω_f ,
 - c. choose a frequency increment, ω_{inc} , and
 - d. set $\omega = \omega_i$.
2. While $\omega < \omega_f$,
 - a. calculate the transfer function matrix at $s=j\omega$. $A_k = C_M(j\omega I - A_M)^{-1} B_M + D_M$ if M is given in state space form. $A_k = M(j\omega)$ if M is given in transfer function form.
 - b. Use Osborne's technique to find the best D matrix at this frequency.
 - c. Calculate $DA_k D^{-1}$.
 - d. Find the maximum singular value of $DA_k D^{-1}$.
 - e. Store the frequency and the corresponding maximum singular value.
 - f. Let $\omega = \omega + \omega_{inc}$.
3. Plot the maximum singular values (from 2.e.) versus the log of the corresponding frequencies.
4. If the singular value plot approaches or crosses unity in any frequency range, and the plot does not look smooth, return to step 1 and use a

smaller frequency increment to more carefully examine the region of interest.

5. μ_c is less than or equal to the largest of the maximum singular values found in 2.e. If $\mu_c < 1$, the system will remain stable in the face of the anticipated uncertainty ($\mu_c < 1/\delta, \delta = 1 \Rightarrow \mu_c < 1$). If $\mu_c > 1$, then the system can handle at least $1/\mu_c$ times the given uncertainty [6].

DEVELOPMENT OF μ_r

The development of μ_c assumed complex uncertainties. For problems with real parameter variations, a less conservative robustness measure may be obtained by considering only real variations.

Jones [2] modified Equation (3) for the case of real uncertainties. He defined μ_r as

$$\mu_r(M) = \min_{\Delta \in X_\delta \cap R^{n \times n}} (\bar{\sigma}(\Delta) : \det(I + M\Delta) = 0)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where the subscript r denotes real variations, and $R^{n \times n}$ is the set of all real square matrices with dimension n. The intersection of X_δ and $R^{n \times n}$ represents the set of all real (as opposed to complex) block diagonal matrices with structure defined by k_{bar} and norm not greater than δ .

Equation (5) is similar to equation (3) in that both represent very difficult optimization problems. To facilitate computation, Jones provides an approximation for μ_r :

$$\mu_r(M) \leq \min_{D \in D} \left[\max_{\Phi} \bar{\sigma} \{ DMD^{-1}\Phi + (DMD^{-1}\Phi)^T \} / 2 \right] \quad (6)$$

where D is the same as in the last section, and $\Phi \in I_q^n$.

Osborne's technique can be used to find the best D matrix to minimize the Frobenius norm of $\{ DMD^{-1}\Phi + (DMD^{-1}\Phi)^T \}$. Again, because the Frobenius norm is an upper bound to the 2-norm, minimizing the Frobenius norm helps to reduce the 2-norm.

ALGORITHM TO APPROXIMATE μ_r

This algorithm is designed to aid in approximating μ_r based on Equation (6) given the transfer function matrix M for a problem having q unique, non-repeated, independent, real uncertainties where the magnitude of each subblock of Δ is bounded by 1.

The algorithm below represents a modification of Algorithm 1. Steps identical to steps in Algorithm 1 are abbreviated.

Algorithm 2

1. For the frequency sweep, choose ω_i , ω_f , and ω_{inc} . Set $\omega = \omega_i$.
2. Set up a $2^q \times q$ matrix where the rows account for the 2^q possible permutations of 1 and -1. Call this PHIT (PHI Total).
3. While $\omega < \omega_f$,
 - a. Calculate the transfer function matrix at $s = j\omega$. Call this A_k .
 - b. Use Osborne's technique to find D.
 - c. For index=1 to 2^q ,
 - 1) Create a diagonal matrix Φ which has the elements of one row of PHIT as its diagonal values. The row of PHIT chosen is determined by the value of index (row # = index).
 - 2) Find the max singular value of $\left[\{ DA_k D^{-1} \Phi + (DA_k D^{-1} \Phi)^T \} / 2 \right]$. Call this SVAM(index).
 - d. Find the maximum value in SVAM. This represents the maximum singular value for this frequency.
 - e. Store the frequency and corresponding maximum singular value.
 - f. Let $\omega = \omega + \omega_{inc}$.
3. Plot the maximum singular values (from 2.e.) versus the log of the corresponding frequencies.
4. Check for frequency ranges that need to be examined more closely.
5. μ_r is less than or equal to the largest of the maximum singular values found in 2.e. If $\mu_r < 1$, the system will remain stable in the face of the given uncertainty. If $\mu_r > 1$, the system can handle at least $1/\mu_r$ times the given uncertainty [6].

EXAMPLE

Figure 2 shows a block diagram of a system defined in [6] and [7]:

Figure 2

where

$$G(s) = \frac{k}{s(s+a)(s+b)}, \quad K(s) = \frac{s+2}{s+10}$$

and k , a , and b are real uncertain parameters. A state space realization for M is

$$A_M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -800 & 0 & 8 \\ 0 & -6 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & -4 & 0 \\ 0 & 800 & 0 & -10 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -80 \\ 0 & .3 & 0 \\ .2 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D_M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A_M & B_M \\ C_M & D_M \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_k \end{bmatrix}$$

and k_{bar} for this system is given as

$$k_{bar} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Using Algorithm 1, μ_c is approximated as

$$\mu_c = .4575$$

Using Algorithm 2, μ_r is approximated as

$$\mu_r = .3685$$

From [6], the exact value for μ_r is

$$\mu_r = .2926$$

Comparing these three results, it is evident that both Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 provide reasonable results despite being conservative.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

The main advantage to calculating the structured singular value via Frobenius norms is the ease of calculation. Both algorithms can be easily programmed [5] to run taking advantage of the matrix manipulation programs currently available.

There are two main disadvantages to the algorithms presented. First, both use Osborne's technique as the optimization tool. Minimizing the Frobenius norm reduces the 2-norm, but does not necessarily minimize it as the theory requires. Because the Frobenius norm is an upper bound on the 2-norm, results for μ_c and μ_r are conservative. Secondly, both algorithms require a frequency sweep. This may become computationally burdensome, and it is always possible to overlook the frequency at which $\mu_c(s)$ reaches its peak value, and therefore obtain an approximation for μ that is too low.

CONCLUSION

Two algorithms have been presented to aid in approximating μ_c and μ_r via Frobenius norms for problems with non-repeated, independent uncertainties. Both algorithms are easily programmable and give results that are reasonably good despite some conservatism.

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